

International Conference on Data Mining and Software Engineering (DMSE 2020)

September 26 ~ 27, 2020, Copenhagen, Denmark

<https://dmse2020.org/>

Scope & Topics

International Conference on Data Mining and Software Engineering (DMSE 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Data mining and Software Engineering. The goal of this conference is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Data mining and modern software engineering concepts and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of data mining and software engineering.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Advanced Topics in Software Engineering
- Data Mining Applications
- Computer Education
- Data Mining in Modeling, Visualization, Personalization and Recommendation
- Data Mining Systems and Platforms, Efficiency, Scalability and Privacy
- Embedded System and Software
- Foundations, Algorithms, Models, and Theory
- Knowledge Processing
- Knowledge-based Systems and Formal Methods
- Languages and Formal Methods
- Managing Software Projects
- Mining Text, Semi-Structured, Spatio-Temporal, Streaming, Graph, Web, Multimedia
- Multimedia and Visual Software Engineering
- Quality Management
- Search Engines and Information Retrieval
- Software Engineering Decision Making
- Software Engineering Practice
- Software Maintenance and Testing
- Software Process
- Web Engineering
- Web-based Education Systems and Learning Applications

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **July 18, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **DMSE 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International Journal of Software Engineering & Applications \(IJSEA\)](#) – ERA Indexed
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)
- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJDMP\)](#)
- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDMS\)](#)
- [Advanced Computing: An International Journal \(ACIJ\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)^{New}](#) – ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline :July 18, 2020**
- Authors Notification : August 20, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : August 28, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : dmse@dmse2020.org or dmsesecretary@gmail.com